

Integrating Domain Knowledge and Large Language Models for Automatic Generation of Function Block-Based PLC Logic in Maritime Systems

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ABSTRACT

The growing complexity of shipboard automation and the expanding scale of IEC 61131-3 control logic have increased the demand for systematic engineering workflows. Traditional practices rely on manual interpretation of Function Design Specifications and expert-driven mapping of field I/O signals to vendor-specific Function Blocks (FBs), resulting in variability in logic quality and significant development effort. While recent advances in large language models (LLMs) have improved general code generation, existing approaches remain insufficient for industrial control systems because they overlook FB semantics, hardware constraints, and ship-specific structural relationships. This study presents a domain-aware framework that integrates LLMs with retrieval-augmented domain knowledge to automatically generate FB-based PLC logic for maritime systems. The framework embeds FB manuals and normalized I/O descriptions into vector stores and incorporates graph-based relational knowledge capturing FB selection rules, cooperation patterns, and symmetry and grouping structures in I/O configurations. Using these structured representations, the pipeline performs FB type selection, instance estimation, parameter assignment, and I/O mapping, after which a rule-based generator produces IEC 61131-3 compliant Structured Text to ensure syntactic and structural correctness. Experiments using control narratives, FB manuals, and I/O datasets from operational ship projects show that relational knowledge significantly improves planning accuracy, enhancing FB identification, instance estimation, and I/O mapping across model scales. The framework produces deployable FB-based logic without model fine-tuning, relying solely on in-context knowledge injection. These results demonstrate that domain-grounded LLM workflows can reduce engineering variability and provide a practical, scalable approach for automating control-logic development in maritime systems.

1. Introduction

The complexity of shipboard control systems has increased rapidly due to stricter environmental regulations and the acceleration of digitalization [7]. Modern vessels contain multiple subsystems—such as propulsion, steering, power management, cooling, and auxiliary equipment—that operate through tightly integrated controllers and communication networks [4]. In this environment, automation software plays a central role in coordinating equipment interaction and maintaining operational safety [17]. As ship systems continue to diversify, the size and intricacy of IEC 61131-3 control logic have grown substantially, increasing the engineering effort required for design, verification, and maintenance.

Most shipboard control logic is implemented using Function Block (FB) and Structured Text (ST) languages [13]. In maritime engineering, the overall control strategy for operating shipboard process equipment is documented in the Function Design Specification (FDS). From this document, specific operational requirements are extracted

as *control narratives*. For example, a narrative for a Starting Air System might state:

“The Starting Air System is composed of three main air compressors that supply compressed air to Start Air Reservoirs. These compressors are automatically operated by the IAS (Integrated Automation System) through a lead/lag control strategy. When the system is in lead/lag mode, the compressor assigned with the highest priority will automatically start when the reservoir pressure falls below the set point. The operator can select the priority order via the IAS. Once all pressure switches return to normal, the running compressor will be automatically stopped by the system logic.”

While such narratives describe the overall control logic, they often lack the specific parameter configurations dictated by the characteristics of the actual target equipment (e.g., varying types of compressor motors). To bridge this gap and minimize implementation discrepancies, engineers utilize FBs, which encapsulate the necessary parameters and logic into reusable modular units. Despite this modular approach, developing FB-based logic still depends heavily on the expertise of individual engineers. Because engineers possess varying levels of understanding regarding specific vendor

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FBs, the manual process of identifying FB types, determining instance counts, and mapping vessel-specific I/O signals frequently leads to incorrect parameter settings or erroneous I/O connections. This process is labor-intensive and ultimately leads to inconsistency across engineers, resulting in variability in logic quality and increased maintenance cost.

Recent advances in large language models (LLMs) have enabled substantial progress in natural-language understanding, code generation, and structured reasoning [5]. However, industrial control languages differ fundamentally from conventional programming languages: they must comply with IEC 61131-3 semantics, vendor-specific FB definitions, and hardware-level I/O constraints. As a result, direct application of LLMs often yields incomplete or structurally invalid control logic. Although previous studies have explored prompt engineering, model adaptation, retrieval-augmented generation (RAG), and multi-agent workflows, most evaluations have been conducted on public datasets or simplified examples that do not reflect the complexity of real automation environments. This gap underscores the need for approaches that incorporate domain-specific context and structural constraints into the generation process.

To address these challenges, we propose an FB-centric generation framework that closely aligns with actual industrial workflows. While previous LLM-based approaches have primarily focused on synthesizing raw ST sequence logic—such as basic conditional statements and mathematical operators—our research shifts the focus toward structural logic design. Specifically, the proposed framework targets the generation of ST code that instantiates predefined FB types, configures their parameters, and establishes inter-block connections, effectively functioning as an executable FB network. Rather than translating natural-language control narratives directly into raw sequence code, the framework uses RAG to retrieve FB definitions, I/O characteristics, and relational knowledge—including FB cooperation patterns and symmetry or grouping structures in I/O signals—and integrates them into a structured planning process. This design allows LLMs to reason about control semantics, determine appropriate FB types and instance counts, and assign parameters and connections in a manner consistent with industrial practices.

Complementing this framework, we conduct a practical evaluation using control narratives extracted from actual ship FDS documents and field I/O lists from operational vessels. This enables assessment under realistic engineering conditions and highlights how domain-grounded retrieval and relational knowledge improve robustness compared to methods tested only on simplified examples. Together, these contributions demonstrate that integrating domain knowledge with structured reasoning substantially enhances the reliability and applicability of LLM-based logic generation in maritime control systems.

Table 1

Classification of Control Code Generation Studies by Key Strategy

Category	Description	Representative Studies
Prompt Engineering	Improving output consistency and accuracy through targeted prompt design and constraints	Kozirolek et al. [10] Tran et al. [15] Zhang & de Sousa [19] Kozirolek et al. [8]
Model-based Adaptation	Training models with domain data to learn control-language syntax and rules	Fakih et al. [3] Ren et al. [14]
RAG	Enhancing code generation using retrieved external domain knowledge	Kozirolek et al. [11] Kozirolek et al. [9]
Intelligent Agents	Generating reliable code via iterative search generation verification cycles	Liu et al. [12] Xia et al. [18] Kersting et al. [6]

2. Related Work

Code generation from natural-language specifications has become a prominent application area for LLMs. Early studies explored the feasibility of translating natural-language instructions into executable code across general-purpose programming languages. Vaithilingam et al. [16] observed that tools such as GitHub Copilot perform well for simple and pattern-based tasks, yet often produce erroneous code when confronted with complex logical dependencies. Chen et al. [1] demonstrated that the Codex model can synthesize working programs directly from natural-language descriptions, while Du et al. [2] conducted structured evaluations of class-level code generation using the ClassEval benchmark. Collectively, these studies highlight the growing capabilities of LLMs in conventional software development.

However, industrial control systems differ fundamentally from general-purpose programming environments. Although LLMs excel at generating general-purpose code due to massive open-source training corpora, industrial languages like IEC 61131-3 suffer from severe data scarcity. Furthermore, generating control logic requires tight physical integration rather than standard software synthesis. IEC 61131-3 languages impose strict syntactic and structural constraints, and ship automation systems require vendor-specific Function Blocks, hardware-aware parameterization, and adherence to equipment-level operational semantics. As a result, generic LLMs prompted only with natural-language instructions cannot reliably generate deployable control logic. To address these challenges, recent research has evolved along four principal strategies, summarized in Table 1.

The first line of work focuses on prompt engineering, where constraints, templates, or few-shot demonstrations are incorporated into prompts to stabilize output quality. Prior studies [10, 15, 19, 8] report that such methods improve accuracy in simple or structurally repetitive tasks but degrade rapidly in scenarios requiring nuanced interpretation of system states or safety-critical conditions.

The second direction, model-based adaptation, fine-tunes LLMs on domain-specific repositories so that syntax rules, FB patterns, and control semantics are implicitly learned. Approaches such as LLM4PLC [3] and MetaIndux-PLC [14] achieve higher correctness by embedding domain knowledge directly in model parameters, often coupled with formal verification techniques. Nevertheless, these methods require substantial proprietary datasets and computational resources, limiting their practicality in industrial settings where data confidentiality and model maintenance pose additional burdens.

The third strategy introduces RAG, enabling LLMs to reference external control libraries, FB documentation, or code templates at inference time. Koziolok et al. [11] demonstrated that LLMs can successfully instantiate function blocks using RAG, bypassing the need for prior training on proprietary PLC libraries. Building on this, workflows like Spec2Control [9] dynamically retrieve external library definitions and predefined control strategies to autonomously generate graphical function block diagrams. However, existing RAG approaches primarily rely on document-level retrieval, which typically extracts isolated text chunks from manuals based solely on semantic similarity. This approach is insufficient for industrial logic, where components are deeply interdependent, as it does not explicitly capture the relational structures—such as FB cooperation rules, mutual exclusivity, or I/O symmetry—that govern real industrial logic.

Finally, agent-based approaches employ iterative cycles of search, generation, validation, and revision. Multi-agent frameworks [12, 18] integrate domain rules, RAG components, and formal or heuristic validators to progressively refine control logic. Recent efforts have extended these cycles to handle proprietary vendor constraints; for instance, Kersting et al. [6] introduced an on-premise coding agent that utilizes real-time compiler feedback to iteratively repair vendor-specific ST code. While these systems show improved robustness, they often require sophisticated orchestration pipelines or depend heavily on post-generation repair loops, and may still fail to account for ship-specific I/O layouts or vendor-specific FB semantics during the initial logic planning phase.

In contrast to prior approaches that primarily synthesize raw ST sequence code using low-level functions, our work shifts toward architectural synthesis. The proposed framework guides the LLM to step-by-step deduce a control architecture structurally equivalent to Function Block Diagrams by combining and configuring pre-built, large-scale FBs that encapsulate comprehensive control functions per control element, mirroring actual industrial practices.

A deterministic, rule-based generator then synthesizes the final executable ST code. To support this process, our RAG mechanism extends beyond surface-level text retrieval by explicitly injecting domain-specific relational knowledge derived from FB manuals and real vessel I/O datasets. By integrating FB selection/cooperation relationships and I/O group/symmetry structures, the framework enables the LLM to perform structured reasoning—a constrained decision-making process governed by relational graphs rather than purely statistical text prediction. Finally, unlike studies relying on synthetic examples, we evaluate our approach using control narratives from operational ship FDS documents and their associated field data, demonstrating its practical effectiveness in handling the rigorous structural constraints of real industrial PLC environments.

3. Proposed Framework

3.1. Overview of the Framework

Implementing, validating, and deploying control logic requires a structured architecture that links multiple functional stages in a coherent manner. Such an architecture can be viewed as a framework that organizes the stepwise procedure and the interactions among its constituent modules. The framework proposed in this study takes control narratives described in the FDS as input and generates consistent and deployable FB-based logic suitable for ship automation systems.

Figure 1 provides an overview of the proposed LLM RAG framework. The architecture is divided into two layers. The upper layer, referred to as the Generation Pipeline, defines the sequential stages that transform natural-language control narratives into an FB-level logic structure and subsequently into IEC 61131-3 Structured Text. To ensure reliable data flow and structural integrity, these pipeline modules exchange information using structured JSON payloads that explicitly define FB types, parameter mappings, and I/O connections. The lower layer, the Knowledge Base and RAG Layer, supplies the domain knowledge required at each stage—FB definitions, I/O descriptions, and relational knowledge—retrieved dynamically through RAG. This section describes how these layers interact and how they collectively support structured logic generation.

FB-level functional reuse is widely adopted in ship control systems to maintain consistency and quality across vessels. However, FB capabilities and configuration options differ across vendors, and several specifications are not publicly available. These challenges prevent LLMs from inferring such knowledge implicitly. To overcome this, we construct a Function Block Vector Store containing embedded FB definitions and example usages, and a Field I/O Vector Store that aggregates tag names, addresses, scaling rules, and vessel-specific signal data. Furthermore, domain-specific relational knowledge—such as FB selection and cooperation rules, as well as symmetry and grouping relationships within I/O signals—is encoded separately so it can guide the interpretation of control narratives and the construction of logic structures.

Figure 1: Overall architecture of the proposed LLM-RAG framework. The upper layer performs FB-centric logic planning and code synthesis, while the lower layer supplies domain knowledge—FB manuals, I/O data, and relational structures—retrieved dynamically through RAG and injected into each stage of the pipeline.

At each stage of the generation pipeline, the required domain information is retrieved from the knowledge base using RAG and incorporated directly into the model’s context. The framework does not rely on domain-specific fine-tuning; instead, it adopts an In-Context Learning (ICL) approach. Rather than updating internal model weights, this ICL mechanism allows the LLM to perform structured reasoning based solely on the instructions, constraints, and dynamically injected domain knowledge provided within the prompt. This design avoids the cost and inflexibility of retraining while enabling rapid adaptation to vessel-specific FB manuals and I/O layouts.

3.2. Domain Knowledge Embedding

In the proposed framework, RAG serves as a core mechanism for identifying the FB types required to implement a given control narrative, estimating the necessary number of instances, and retrieving the information needed to link the logic to actual I/O signals. To enable semantic retrieval of such domain knowledge, it is essential to project the data into a vector space. In this study, we embed FB manuals and the I/O Signal List using a deep learning-based embedding model and construct them as vector stores. Control narratives extracted from the FDS are embedded in the same manner, allowing similarity computation between embedding vectors to retrieve relevant FB type candidates and associated I/O information.

Given a control narrative q , the retrieval of FB type and I/O candidate sets in the embedding space is defined as follows:

$$C_F = \text{Top-}k(\cos(\phi(q), \phi(f)), f \in F) \quad (1)$$

$$C_I = \text{Top-}k(\cos(\phi(q), \phi(i)), i \in I) \quad (2)$$

Here, ϕ denotes the embedding function, while F and I represent the sets of FB type documents and I/O entries, respectively. The choice of embedding granularity (e.g., section, subsection, paragraph) directly affects retrieval performance, making proper selection crucial depending on the data characteristics and intended use.

To illustrate the semantic richness and complexity of the data projected into the vector store, Table 2 provides an excerpt of an FB definition (IAS_MT1) used for motor control. As shown, a single industrial FB typically encompasses an extensive array of interface fields—for instance, IAS_MT1 consists of 60 specific inputs, parameters, and outputs in total. This definition includes a comprehensive natural-language description alongside these detailed pin semantics.

While capturing these unique operational characteristics is essential, vendor manuals and FB structures frequently include redundant elements common across multiple FB types, such as generic alarm handling, standard interlock logic,

Table 2
Excerpt of the IAS_MT1 Function Block Used for Embedding

Category	Content
Description	This function block is used to monitor and control individual motors such as pumps, compressors, and conveyors in automation systems. It supports both manual and automatic operation modes, with local or remote control selection. The block manages motor operations including start, stop, trip, and blackout handling, while supervising status, alarms, power availability, and interlock conditions.
Inputs (Total 20)	RUN (Running status feedback), ASTART/ASTOP (Auto mode commands), ILOCK (Interlock input), etc.
Params (Total 21)	PMXTMST (Max time for start feedback), PTRIPO (Shutdown option), etc.
Outputs (Total 19)	START/STOP (Command to motor starter), ERROR (General error indicator), etc.

Tag Name	Description	Signal Type	MIN	MAX	Unit
MC_RPM_Y	M/E T/C RPM	AI	0	20000	rpm
MC_LOAD1_Y	M/E LOAD FROM EICU	AI	0	120	%
MC_XI3_Y	ACTUAL SF LOAD(XC6028)	AI	0	120	%
MC_PI1_Y	SF SUPPLY PRESSURE SET POINT	AI	0	100	bar
MC_PT6043_Y	M/E RVT PRESS	AI	0	100	bar
MC_TT6044_Y	M/E RVT TEMP	AI	-50	100	°C
MC_PT6017_Y	LFF SUPPLY PRESS	AI	0	100	bar
MC_PT6006_Y	LFF INLET PRESS	AI	0	100	bar
MC_PT8708_Y	M/E T/C BACK PRESSURE	AI	0	100	mbar
GA_TIAH1_Y	NO.1 GEN. WINDING(R) TEMP	AI	0	200	°C
GA_TIAH2_Y	NO.1 GEN. WINDING(S) TEMP	AI	0	200	°C
GA_TIAH3_Y	NO.1 GEN. WINDING(T) TEMP	AI	0	200	°C
GA_XO_Y	NO.1 G/E LOAD (FOR AWG)	AI	0	120	%
GA_XI3_Y	NO.1 G/E AWG V/V POSITION	AI	0	100	%

Figure 2: Example of ship I/O data. Each I/O entry contains attributes such as tag name, description, unit, and minimum/maximum values. In this study, the description field is normalized into natural-language form to improve embedding quality.

and trip configurations. Directly embedding these repetitive interface fields in their entirety dilutes the discriminative power of the embeddings and degrades retrieval accuracy. Therefore, we apply a selective embedding approach: universally common I/O pins, generic parameters (e.g., standard alarms and trips), and overlapping explanations are filtered out. Only the core descriptions and interface signals that uniquely differentiate each FB type are retained and embedded. This significantly reduces noise and enhances semantic matching.

In contrast, I/O Signal Lists often rely on fragmented abbreviations and technical shorthand, lacking the semantic richness required for direct alignment with natural-language control narratives. As illustrated in Fig. 2, these context-limited and inconsistently formatted descriptions degrade embedding-based retrieval performance. To mitigate this, we employ a preprocessing step that normalizes and enriches I/O descriptions into natural-language sentences via LLM-based rephrasing. This expansion of technical shorthand into contextual descriptions ensures robust semantic matching and reduces ambiguity caused by inconsistent nomenclature.

3.3. Domain Knowledge Relation Extraction

Embedding-based retrieval effectively identifies semantically relevant FBs and I/O signals, but similarity alone cannot capture the structural dependencies that characterize real industrial control systems. FBs and field I/O signals operate not as isolated components but within established engineering patterns and system constraints. Without explicitly modeling these relationships, retrieval may produce semantically plausible yet structurally invalid candidates. To address this limitation, the proposed framework extracts relational knowledge from domain data and integrates it into the logic generation process to ensure architectural consistency.

FB-level relationships arise from vendor specifications and established implementation practices. These relationships fall into two categories: selection relationships and cooperation relationships. Selection relationships represent cases in which multiple FBs provide alternative functionalities but must not be used simultaneously, such as a general-purpose motor FB versus a VFD motor FB. Cooperation relationships describe FBs that must be paired to realize a complete operational behavior, such as a valve command FB combined with a PID controller. Modeling these relationships constrains the LLM to valid FB combinations and prevents architectural conflicts during planning.

I/O-level relational knowledge further refines the interpretation of retrieved signals. We distinguish between group relationships and symmetry relationships. Group relationships represent sets of signals that must jointly appear to support a specific function; for example, valve control typically requires open/close commands along with a position feedback signal. Symmetry relationships capture mirrored or repeated structures frequently found in shipboard instrumentation, such as Port/Starboard or No. 1/No. 2 arrangements. Incorporating these relationships enables the system to interpret the structural context of I/O data rather than relying solely on semantic similarity.

Symmetry relationships can be extracted directly using predefined indicators such as equipment numbering or location-based suffixes. Group relationships, however, vary significantly across equipment types and cannot be predefined universally. Extracting them is inherently challenging due to the semi-structured nature of industrial I/O lists, where leading tokens typically identify the primary equipment (e.g., “NO.1 AUX BOILER”) and trailing tokens specify operational attributes (e.g., “RUN”). To infer these structures naturally, we introduce a group-key selection algorithm that iteratively prunes trailing tokens. This approach isolates the core equipment identity while avoiding over-truncation that could erroneously merge distinct equipment groups.

Algorithm 1 presents this process. Taking a pre-tokenized sequence T of an I/O description, it determines the optimal group boundary by evaluating its frequency against the entire description set D :

- **Lines 2–3:** Processing in reverse, backward pruning systematically removes functional attributes to isolate the core equipment name.

Algorithm 1: Group Key Selection Algorithm

Input: Token sequence $T[0..N-1]$, symmetry position pos_{sym} , description set D
Output: Group key key or None

```

1  $key \leftarrow \text{None}$ ,  $prev\_count \leftarrow 0$ ;
2 for  $i \leftarrow N-1$  to 2 do
3    $s \leftarrow$  concatenate tokens  $T[0..i]$ ;
4   if  $i = pos_{sym}$  then
5      $\lfloor$  break ;
6    $match\_count \leftarrow |\{desc \in D \mid s \subseteq desc\}|$ ;
7   if  $key = \text{None}$  then
8     if  $match\_count > 0$  then
9        $key \leftarrow s$ ;
10       $prev\_count \leftarrow match\_count$ ;
11  else
12    if  $match\_count > prev\_count$  then
13      if  $prev\_count > 1$  then
14         $\lfloor$  break ;
15       $key \leftarrow s$ ;
16       $prev\_count \leftarrow match\_count$ ;
17    else if  $match\_count = prev\_count$  and
18       $match\_count > 0$  then
19       $\lfloor$   $key \leftarrow s$ ;
19 return  $key$ ;

```

- **Lines 4–6:** The process halts immediately at the explicit symmetry position (pos_{sym}) to prevent physically distinct equipment instances (e.g., “NO.1” and “NO.2”) from being merged.
- **Lines 7–18:** This is the core boundary-detection logic. An increase in $match_count$ upon pruning indicates a transition to a broader grouping. If a valid functional group was already established ($prev_count > 1$), a further increase implies overgeneralization. The algorithm then halts and retains the most specific group key.

For instance, given the input “NO.1 AUX BOILER RUN”, the algorithm first evaluates the full string, then prunes “RUN” to evaluate “NO.1 AUX BOILER”. Since multiple I/O signals share this prefix, $match_count$ increases. With $prev_count$ initially 1, it identifies “NO.1 AUX BOILER” as a valid key. If it subsequently prunes “BOILER” to evaluate “NO.1 AUX”, $match_count$ jumps again. Because a group was already established ($prev_count > 1$), this triggers the early stopping mechanism, safeguarding the optimal equipment boundary.

This relational extraction mechanism identifies recurring equipment-specific expressions that cannot be reliably captured through embeddings alone. The extracted group keys support the clustering of I/O signals into meaningful functional sets, while symmetry relationships enable accurate expansion for mirrored or repeated configurations. Together,

these relational structures strengthen the framework’s ability to estimate FB instances, identify required inputs and outputs, and generate structurally coherent mappings between FB pins and real-world I/O data, resulting in more accurate and complete logic generation than similarity-based retrieval alone.

3.4. Module-Level Operation of the Framework

This section describes the operational flow of each module in the proposed automatic generation framework and explains their roles in the overall control-logic generation process. The framework takes a control narrative as input and proceeds through four sequential stages—logic planning, FB parameter assignment, I/O mapping, and code generation. Each module operates independently while interacting with the RAG-based knowledge base, forming a continuous pipeline.

3.4.1. Logic Planning

Transforming control narratives into an FB-based structure requires identifying the necessary FB types and determining their instance counts. Prior studies have focused on converting natural-language requirements directly into ST code, but such approaches cannot ensure consistency in industrial environments where FB-centered architectures are standard. To overcome this limitation, we design a logic planning module that produces structured FB plans. We define an FB plan as a structured specification that prescribes the sequence of FB implementations, where each entry includes the selected FB type, its required instance count, and the functional rationale (purpose) derived from the control narrative.

In our framework, all LLM-based operations are executed through a prompt construction function \mathcal{P} , which transforms raw domain data and instructions into a structured natural-language prompt. To emphasize that the outputs are generated through model inference rather than deterministic identities, we denote the retrieval of a response using the assignment operator (\leftarrow).

The planning process proceeds in two steps. First, candidate FB types are retrieved from the selective embedding-based FB store, forming a set C_F . The LLM then receives a prompt \mathcal{P} composed of C_F together with FB relationship knowledge KG_{FB} (e.g., selection rules and functional constraints) and derives the set of final FB types $P_{FB} = \{f_1, f_2, \dots, f_m\}$:

$$P_{FB} \leftarrow LLM(\mathcal{P}(C_F, KG_{FB}, q)) \quad (3)$$

As observed in the logic for a compressed air system, P_{FB} might include IAS_DS (a coordination block for duty/standby management) and IAS_MT1 (a block for individual motor control).

Second, the system determines the required number of instances for each selected FB type. The LLM processes a prompt \mathcal{P} incorporating I/O retrieval results C_I and I/O relationship knowledge KG_{IO} to compute the final FB instance

plan P , defined as a set of tuples $P = \{(f_i, n_i, r_i) \mid f_i \in P_{FB}\}$, where $n_i \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ is the instance count and r_i is the rationale:

$$P \leftarrow LLM(\mathcal{P}(C_I, KG_{IO}, q, P_{FB})) \quad (4)$$

For example, if a narrative specifies a lead/lag operation for three compressors, P would specify one instance of IAS_DS and three instances of IAS_MT1 (one for each physical unit). This structured output ensures that the plan reflects both the structural meaning of the control narrative and the real hardware configuration.

3.4.2. FB Parameter Assignment and I/O Connection

Industrial FBs contain numerous parameters and pins that encapsulate complex control functions. For each FB instance f_i in the plan P , the LLM assigns specific values to its internal parameters and establishes signal-flow links between FBs and field I/O signals through structured prompting.

For each FB $f_i \in P$, the LLM processes a prompt \mathcal{P} constructed from its definition σ_i and the control narrative q , obtaining a parameter configuration set $\phi_i = \{(p_{i,j}, v_{i,j})\}$:

$$\phi_i \leftarrow LLM(\mathcal{P}(\sigma_i, q)), \quad \forall f_i \in P \quad (5)$$

For example, if the control narrative explicitly dictates a “lead/lag control strategy,” the LLM matches this requirement (q) against the parameter specifications of the IAS_DS block (σ_i) to infer the functional mode, assigning PFTYPE = 1 (Lead/Lag) instead of 0 (Duty/Standby). Conversely, for operational parameters omitted from the narrative, the LLM leverages the descriptive metadata in σ_i to assign contextually appropriate default values. For instance, although the narrative does not specify a blackout recovery time, the LLM sets PBLKRTM = 10 based on the FB’s parameter description, autonomously enforcing a 10-second safety delay before motor restarts.

When multiple FBs are used together, the LLM generates a set of internal signal-flow relationships $\phi_{link} = \{(pin_{in}, pin_{out})\}$, defining the internal logical wiring between FB instances:

$$\phi_{link} \leftarrow LLM(\mathcal{P}(P, \sigma_i, q)) \quad (6)$$

For instance, the coordination logic is established by linking IAS_MT1#1.DSOUT to IAS_DS#1.DSIN1.

To incorporate physical I/O constraints, retrieved I/O candidates C_I are added to the prompt \mathcal{P} . The LLM maps FB pins to valid I/O points, producing an I/O mapping set $\phi_{link_io} = \{(pin, tag)\}$, where $tag \in C_I$ is a physical field signal:

$$\phi_{link_io} \leftarrow LLM(\mathcal{P}(C_I, KG_{IO}, \phi_{link}, q)) \quad (7)$$

This stage bridges the abstracted logic with real-world signals, such as mapping the CTRON pin of IAS_DS to the physical start signal “SERVICE AIR COMP. START”. The resulting ϕ_{link_io} forms an intermediate representation (IR) passed to the code generation stage.

3.4.3. Parameter Validation and Code Generation

Although the IR generated by the LLM captures the semantic structure of the control narrative, it does not fully guarantee correctness with respect to controller constraints or data-type rules. To bridge the gap between probabilistic LLM outputs and deterministic industrial requirements, we define the IR as a structured set $IR = \{P, \{\phi_i\}, \phi_{link_io}\}$. This IR undergoes a rigorous syntactic and semantic validation process before the final code synthesis.

The validation module checks parameter types, ranges, and units against the formal FB definitions σ_i . Specifically, it ensures that all assigned values $v_{i,j} \in \phi_i$ satisfy the boundary conditions and data-type constraints defined in the vendor-specific library. Out-of-range or inconsistent parameters are automatically corrected based on predefined safety policies. Similarly, type mismatches or directional inconsistencies in FB connections are resolved or pruned to ensure executability within the target industrial controller environment.

The validated IR is then passed to the rule-based ST code generator ($CodeGen_{rule}$), which translates the high-level structural plan into vendor-specific, IEC 61131-3 compliant ST code. Unlike LLM-based approaches that synthesize raw sequence logic, $CodeGen_{rule}$ follows a deterministic template-based approach to ensure that the resulting code accurately instantiates the defined FB network:

$$ST_i \leftarrow CodeGen_{rule}(\phi_i, \phi_{link_io}, \sigma_i, f_i), \quad \forall f_i \in P \quad (8)$$

$CodeGen_{rule}$ references FB defaults and static parameters to construct variable declarations and execution sections, preventing errors such as missing variables or type conflicts. By combining LLM-based semantic synthesis with rule-based formal verification, the resulting ST code achieves higher stability and lower error probability than direct text-based code-generation approaches.

4. Performance Evaluation

4.1. Evaluation Metrics and Experimental Criteria

The proposed framework consists of three stages—RAG-based retrieval, planning, and FB-centered code generation. To evaluate each stage quantitatively, we define metrics that reflect the characteristics of each component. The overall assessment focuses on three aspects: embedding-based retrieval accuracy, relation-informed planning accuracy, and structural correctness of the FB-based code.

First, for the RAG retrieval stage, we apply Recall@K to measure the retrieval inclusion effectiveness. In this context,

Recall@K evaluates whether the retrieval module successfully captures the necessary domain knowledge within the top-K candidates, ensuring that the ground-truth information is available for the LLM’s final decision-making. The primary goal is to provide a noise-filtered context that eliminates the vast majority of irrelevant data while retaining a highly relevant candidate set, thereby allowing the LLM to effectively reason within a constrained and accurate search space.

Second, for the planning stage, we measure how accurately the LLM identifies FB types and determines instance counts. To ensure deterministic accuracy, the LLM’s outputs are evaluated against reference control logic manually verified by domain experts. The criteria for success include the correct identification of FB types and the exact determination of instance counts that match the actual shipboard configuration. FB type prediction is evaluated using Precision, Recall, and F1 Score, while instance-count accuracy is measured using Exact Match Ratio (EMR). To analyze the contribution of structural domain knowledge, we compare performance with and without providing FB selection/cooperation constraints and I/O group/symmetry relations.

Third, for the code-generation stage, we evaluate whether the generated FB-based control logic achieves deployable structural completeness. Unlike prior work, which primarily used compilation success as a proxy for correctness, our assessment focuses on the alignment between the generated model and the actual implemented logic across four structural dimensions: FB types, instance counts, inter-block signal flows, and field I/O connections. We compare FB-connection accuracy and parameter-setting accuracy under different planning conditions to assess how structured planning and relation knowledge contribute to a result that consistently follows the established control architecture.

By integrating Recall@K, Precision/Recall/F1, and EMR, the evaluation framework provides a comprehensive assessment of how effectively the proposed method supports domain-knowledge retrieval, FB-based design, and structurally consistent code generation.

4.2. Experimental Environment and Dataset

In this study, we evaluated the proposed framework using both an on-premise inference environment and a cloud-based managed LLM environment. The on-premise setup allows SLM (small language model) to be executed locally, which is beneficial for data sovereignty and reproducibility, while the cloud setup enables immediate access to state-of-the-art large-scale LLMs. Considering the security requirements and offline operation needs of ship control systems, both environments were included in the experiments.

For the on-premise experiments, we deployed an SLM stack, whereas in the cloud environment we used a managed LLM service (AWS Bedrock). Both environments shared the same orchestration layer based on LangChain and used ChromaDB as the vector store. We also applied an identical prompt structure and evaluation procedure to ensure fair

Table 3

Experimental environment for LLM-based code generation

Item	Configuration
GPU	NVIDIA RTX A5000 × 2 (24 GB each)
LLM framework	LangChain 0.3.26
Local SLM tool	Ollama 0.11.4
Local SLM models	llama3:8b, gemma:7b, mistral:7b
Managed LLM (MaaS) MaaS models	AWS Bedrock Titan, Claude 3.5 Haiku, Llama 3 70B, Nova Pro
RAG vector store	ChromaDB 1.0.15
Embedding model	all-MiniLM-L6-v2

comparison across environments. The overall experimental configuration is summarized in Table 3.

The FB (Function Block) dataset used in the experiments was constructed from actual ship control system manuals. Each FB serves as a high-density structural control unit, featuring an average of 43.5 pins. While only a subset of these pins are directly mapped to physical field I/O, the majority are critical for internal parameter configuration, inter-block signal coordination, and diagnostic monitoring. The functional characteristics of the 15 representative FBs used in our evaluation—covering the essential operation, protection, and safety logic of maritime systems—are summarized in Table 4. The control-narrative dataset consisted of 35 control narratives carefully extracted from actual FDS documents of real-world vessel projects. In practice, an FDS contains highly complex tables and diagrams spanning hundreds of pages. For this research, we specifically extracted 35 representative descriptive narratives to evaluate the framework’s ability to synthesize logic by bridging natural language with domain-specific knowledge (FBs and I/Os). Although the average narrative length of 474 characters may appear modest, these narratives represent a significant engineering challenge due to the high density of “implicit domain knowledge.” Industrial specifications often omit details such as feedback timeouts, physical signal delays, or specific interlock options, as these are traditionally handled by engineers during on-site commissioning. Correctly reconstructing these missing complexities from a brief narrative is a non-trivial task for LLMs.

Our framework addresses this by focusing on the intelligent selection and configuration of pre-designed FBs that encapsulate these industrial complexities. On average, each narrative involved 2.1 FB instances and 6.3 field I/O connections. The number of instances per task varies from a single FB to as many as 10, particularly when multiple blocks such as VFD, PID, and lead/lag units must be combined or when the logic involves multiple symmetric equipment units. Considering that each FB features 43.5 pins, the model effectively reasons over 90 functional interface points per

Table 4
Summary of representative FBs used in the experiments

FB Name	Functional Summary
IAS_MT1	Controls individual motors with status/alarm supervision.
IAS_DS	Manages duty/standby and lead/lag coordination for up to four motors.
IAS_VFD	Controls Variable Frequency Drives for precise motor speed and torque management.
IAS_VVB VVC	Controls on/off or proportional (0–100%) valve positions with feedback monitoring.
IAS_VVT	Manages valve actuators using pulse-based logic and deadband control.
IAS_PID	Performs closed-loop PID control for various process variables.
IAS_TK	Calculates tank level/volume using dual-sensor inputs and sounding tables.
IAS_CSDT	Handles surge display and trend data acquisition for specialized cooling systems.
IAS_CB	Monitors and controls electrical circuit breakers with PMS visualization.
ALMCOMM	Manages communication redundancy and detects network/module faults.
IAS_SLH	Provides hierarchical safety/interlock logic for Emergency Shutdown (ESD).
IAS_FX	Performs 20-point linear interpolation for custom sensor scaling.
IAS_LH8	Latches and logs activation/reset times for multiple binary input signals.

test case, ensuring that the generated logic is not just syntactically correct but functionally deployable in real maritime environments.

4.3. Accuracy Evaluation of RAG with Different Embedding Strategies

This section experimentally analyzes how different domain-knowledge embedding strategies affect the performance of RAG-based retrieval, which forms a core component of the proposed framework. The primary objective of the retrieval stage is to ensure “inclusion accuracy”—guaranteeing that the ground-truth domain knowledge is present within the candidate set provided to the LLM. Rather than identifying a single final answer, this stage serves as a context-preparer that filters out noise from the extensive domain database while ensuring the necessary information remains accessible for the LLM’s subsequent reasoning.

The experiments were conducted by providing identical control narratives as inputs to the RAG module and measuring retrieval accuracy using Recall@K. To assess correctness, each retrieved result was compared against a

ground-truth (GT) mapping list manually verified by domain experts with extensive experience in maritime control systems. Recall@K is well suited for this task as it reflects the probability that the LLM will have access to the correct information within its prompt context.

Figure 3a shows the Recall performance for the FB embedding strategies. The first approach (baseline) embeds only representative functional descriptions, whereas the second includes all field-level descriptions. The third approach removes redundant text—such as repeated alarm or interlock explanations—before embedding. Compared to the baseline, the redundancy-filtered approach showed a consistent performance gain, achieving over 90% recall at $K = 5$. This indicates that eliminating cross-FB noise is crucial for enhancing the discriminability of high-density domain manuals.

Figure 3b presents the results for IO embedding strategies. IO descriptions are often written in heavily abbreviated forms, which typical embedding models cannot effectively map to natural language narratives. While simple abbreviation expansion provided a marginal improvement over the raw-abbreviation baseline, it was insufficient for bridging the semantic gap. In contrast, converting IO descriptions into natural-language sentences using an SLM (small language model) and then embedding them produced consistently higher recall. Despite the risk of occasional rewriting errors, this strategy significantly improved the inclusion of the ground truth within the candidate set, effectively reducing the search space from 2,382 candidates to a manageable context for the LLM.

Overall, the experiments demonstrate that domain knowledge embedding strategies have a direct and substantial influence on the retrieval performance of RAG. By maximizing the inclusion accuracy of the correct domain context, the RAG module functions as a robust context-preparer that empowers the LLM to perform structurally accurate planning and code generation.

4.4. Accuracy Evaluation of Planning with Graph-Based Knowledge

The planning stage takes control narratives extracted from the vessel FDS and determines the appropriate set of FBs and their instance counts. To improve performance, it is essential to supply the LLM with only the most relevant information while excluding unnecessary details. In this study, two strategies were applied to enhance planning accuracy. First, for FB type selection, RAG was used to retrieve only relevant FB candidates, and this set was augmented with graph-based knowledge that captures selection and cooperation relationships between FBs. Second, for determining the number of FB instances, IO signals retrieved via RAG were supplemented with predefined symmetry and group relations extracted from the full IO dataset, reducing both missing and over-expanded IO mappings.

Figure 4(a) visualizes the selection (red dashed lines) and cooperation (blue solid lines) relationships between FBs. To operationalize the conceptual relationships defined

(a) Recall@K performance across FB embedding strategies

(b) Recall@K performance across IO embedding strategies

Figure 3: Retrieval performance under different embedding strategies. Subfigure (a) compares FB manual embeddings, and subfigure (b) evaluates IO description representations. The results show that removing redundant FB text and transforming IO descriptions into natural language significantly improves Recall@K.

(a) FB selection/cooperation relationship graph

(b) IO group and symmetry relationship graph

Figure 4: Domain relationship structures used to enhance planning accuracy. Subfigure (a) presents FB-level selection and cooperation relations that constrain valid FB combinations, while subfigure (b) shows IO-level group and symmetry relations that support consistent instance estimation and prevent missing or redundant IO mappings.

in Section 3.3, these constraints are statically modeled as directed knowledge graphs. Unlike the I/O relationships that are dynamically inferred per vessel via Algorithm 1, the FB relationship graph was constructed manually by aggregating historical implementation datasets from past vessel projects and integrating the validated heuristic knowledge of maritime domain experts. Once constructed, this relation graph can be reused across different vessel projects and easily extended as new FBs or functionalities are added. Providing this structured relational knowledge during planning constrains the design space and improves the stability and consistency of FB type selection.

Figure 4(b) illustrates examples of group and symmetry relations extracted from IO data. Symmetry relations arise from identifier patterns such as NO1/NO2, PORT/STBD, or suffixes like (P)/(S), which commonly appear in duplicated or mirrored equipment layouts. Group relations identify IO signals

that form a coherent functional set within the same equipment (e.g., open/close commands and position feedback for valve control). Using the proposed extraction algorithm, a total of 692 symmetry relations and 118 group relations were identified. These structural cues play an essential role in determining instance counts and mapping IO signals to FB pins.

To evaluate the effect of relational knowledge, we prepared multiple prompt configurations with different combinations of RAG retrieval results and relationship graphs, and tested them across three local SLMs (7B–8B) and four cloud-based LLMs. Figure 5 summarizes the results. Overall, models performed best when supplied with only the essential retrieved information along with the necessary relationship knowledge. Nova-based models, in particular, showed substantial improvements in Precision and F1 Score when FB relationship graphs were included, as the graph prevented the simultaneous selection of mutually exclusive

Figure 5: Comparison of FB planning accuracy under different knowledge-injection strategies, showing how FB relationship graphs and IO relational knowledge affect F1 performance across models.

Table 5

Accuracy of FB instance estimation under different relationship-knowledge settings (EMR %)

MODE	llama3	gemma	Mistral	titan	Claude Haiku	llama3 70B	Nova Pro
base	52.4	61.9	59.5	57.1	90.5	71.4	78.6
group	47.6	57.1	61.9	54.8	88.1	69.0	76.2
sym	54.8	54.8	69.0	61.9	90.5	69.0	76.2
all	47.6	57.1	59.5	69.0	92.9	78.6	78.6

FBs. Conversely, providing the full FB list degraded Precision, as irrelevant FBs were often selected.

After selecting the FB types, the next task is to determine the correct number of FB instances. Accurate instance estimation requires interpreting the IO signals associated with each equipment. We measured Exact Match Ratio (EMR) across four settings: (1) using IO information only (base), (2) adding group relations (group), (3) adding symmetry relations (sym), and (4) adding both relations (all). The results are shown in Table 5.

Claude models consistently achieved the highest EMR (above 90% in all modes). Llama3-70B and Nova Pro also exceeded 70% on average. In contrast, Titan and the SLMs showed lower accuracy. Instance estimation requires integrating multiple sources of domain knowledge—FB field specifications, IO signal attributes, symmetry/group relations—which is challenging for SLMs. These models frequently overestimated instance counts due to incorrect IO interpretation, while larger models effectively leveraged relational knowledge.

Across all models, symmetry relations (sym) provided the most stable performance gains, whereas group relations (group) improved performance mainly in larger models but sometimes degraded accuracy in SLMs. This indicates that different relationship types place different cognitive demands on the model, and that the usefulness of each relation depends on model capacity.

In summary, determining FB instance counts is a complex task requiring integrated reasoning across control narratives, FB semantics, IO characteristics, and IO relationship structures. The results show that relational knowledge significantly improves planning accuracy, but the optimal knowledge-injection strategy varies by model scale and domain understanding.

4.5. Code Generation and Accuracy Evaluation

Prior studies on ST-based control code generation typically guide LLMs to implement the required functionality directly and then evaluate performance based on whether the generated code compiles successfully. In contrast, the proposed framework preserves the IEC 61131-3 ST syntax while structuring control logic around FBs. Rather than allowing the LLM to generate full code, the model is responsible for determining the key design parameters—such as FB types, instance counts, parameter values, and inter-block/IO connections—that effectively form an executable FB network. The final ST code is produced by a rule-based generator (*CodeGen_{rule}*), ensuring domain conformity and structural consistency.

It is important to clarify that the LLM does not merely identify FBs or generate static diagrams; rather, it performs the high-level engineering reasoning required to derive a complete structural plan (Intermediate Representation). Because of this design, compilation success alone is not a meaningful metric. Therefore, we evaluate code-generation accuracy based on the correctness of the inferred FB network architecture against the expected design.

We evaluated the system using all 35 control-narrative tasks described in Section 4.2. Each task was assessed by comparing the LLM-derived FB parameters and connections against the reference industrial logic. The following experimental conditions were compared:

- **No Planning:** FB type selection, instance estimation, parameter assignment, and inter-block connections are all inferred in a single step.
- **Planning:** FB types and instance counts are fixed during the planning stage; the code generation stage performs only parameter assignment and connection inference.
- **Planning + KG:** The planning stage additionally incorporates group and symmetry relationships to support instance estimation and IO mapping.

Table 6 summarizes the performance across four cloud-based LLMs. Across all models, incorporating the planning stage improved accuracy, demonstrating that establishing an FB structure beforehand stabilizes code generation. Notably, for larger models capable of processing complex structured context, injecting relational knowledge (KG) during the planning stage yielded a consistent accuracy gain of approximately 2.3–2.7 percentage points. This uniform improvement indicates that relational constraints provide a robust reasoning foundation, effectively guiding the models

Table 6

Code-generation accuracy with and without planning and relationship knowledge (%)

Condition	Claude Haiku	Llama3-70B	Nova Pro	Titan
No Planning	79.5	69.4	71.8	53.8
Planning	86.2	74.2	75.5	58.5
Planning + KG	88.9	76.6	77.8	60.9

to adhere to industrial logic patterns regardless of their underlying architecture.

Overall, the results demonstrate that incorporating a planning stage provides consistent improvements in code-generation accuracy regardless of model scale. These findings indicate that an FB-centric planning-based approach offers higher reliability and structural consistency in industrial control environments compared to conventional LLM-driven direct code generation, bridging the gap between natural-language control narratives and executable industrial logic.

5. Discussion

5.1. Interpretation of Experimental Results

The experimental results show that the quality of automatic control-logic generation is significantly improved when integrated with diverse domain knowledge, rather than relying on natural language processing alone. In particular, the accuracy of FB instance estimation and code generation was enhanced when additional information—such as IO signals, FB field specifications, and IO relationship structures—was incorporated. These tasks require complex domain reasoning, which made the limitations of SLMs more pronounced, while larger cloud-based models showed greater stability and consistency.

The effect of injecting relational knowledge also varied with model scale. Symmetry relations, which capture structural patterns such as equipment numbering, consistently improved performance across most models. In contrast, group relations yielded mixed results: in some cases, SLMs misinterpreted complex group structures, occasionally leading to performance degradation. However, larger cloud-based LLMs effectively utilized these relational cues to achieve synergistic performance gains.

This distinction was most evident in the final stage of generating full FB parameter settings and connections, where LLM-scale models showed an accuracy improvement of approximately 2.3–2.7 percentage points by leveraging structured domain knowledge. These findings highlight that while relational knowledge is a useful tool for constraining the design space, its effectiveness is closely tied to the reasoning capacity of the underlying model. The proposed IO group–relation extraction method further contributed to this by reliably identifying repeated patterns, thereby enhancing instance estimation and IO mapping accuracy.

5.2. Limitations

Although the study demonstrates the effectiveness of an FB-centered logic generation framework, several functional limitations remain.

First, the framework focuses primarily on FB-based code generation, whereas real industrial control systems often require additional preprocessing and postprocessing logic beyond FB boundaries. Such logic includes signal handling, data conversion, and exception management, which are commonly implemented using ST sequence logic. Relying solely on FB networks may not cover all operational nuances.

Second, the test cases were constructed from control narratives manually extracted from vessel FDS documents. In practice, control requirements are often distributed across multiple chapters, written inconsistently, or contain redundancy. Extracting control logic accurately from such complex, unstructured documentation without human intervention remains a significant challenge.

5.3. Threats to Validity

A primary internal threat to validity is the assumption that the Function Block Vector Store contains a complete set of FB types necessary to implement the target control logic. If a specific FB type or custom vendor logic is missing from the library, the framework may attempt to force an incorrect mapping or fail to generate a valid architecture. This reliance emphasizes the need for continuously updated and verified vendor manuals in real-world deployments.

Regarding external validity and generalizability, this study was evaluated exclusively on maritime control narratives. While the core methodology—leveraging semantic FB definitions and hierarchical I/O relationships—can theoretically be extended to other domains utilizing IEC 61131-3 PLCs (such as water treatment or power generation), achieving this would require adapting the domain-specific I/O naming conventions and relation extraction algorithms to the target industry.

5.4. Future Work

Future research will focus on developing hybrid synthesis methods that integrate FB-based logic with ST sequence logic to achieve broader operational coverage. Furthermore, advancing automated techniques to parse and normalize raw, unstructured FDS documents remains a priority to address structural inconsistencies and diverse terminology. These efforts will strengthen the scalability and reliability of LLM-based automation across maritime and various other industrial control domains.

6. Conclusion

This study presented a framework that integrates LLMs with domain-specific knowledge through RAG to support the structural logic design of FB-based PLC logic for ship control systems. Unlike prior approaches that focused on the direct translation of natural language into raw sequence

code, the proposed framework shifts the focus toward architectural synthesis. By using the LLM as a high-level engineering reasoner to derive structural plans and employing a rule-based generator for deterministic ST code production, the framework ensures both functional flexibility and vendor-compliant structural consistency.

The results of this study indicate that providing all domain information to the LLM in a single prompt is less effective than a structured, stepwise injection of specific knowledge. Specifically, we found that planning accuracy improves significantly when the model is provided with targeted knowledge graphs at each reasoning stage. Furthermore, for effective RAG performance, it was observed that I/O descriptions—which often consist of abbreviations or semi-structured fragments—should be transformed into natural-language sentences to ensure semantic alignment. Similarly, for FB documentation containing highly repetitive or generic interface information, selectively embedding only the parameters and pins that uniquely define the block's functional characteristics proved essential for reducing noise and enhancing retrieval precision.

Experimental results from 35 representative maritime control narratives demonstrate that this structured integration of domain knowledge significantly improves performance across FB type selection, instance estimation, and I/O mapping. While smaller local models occasionally struggled with complex group relations, symmetry relations provided stable improvements across all model scales. Notably, for larger LLMs, the injection of relational knowledge into the planning stage resulted in consistent accuracy gains, proving that structured domain cues effectively constrain the reasoning space to produce deployable industrial logic.

The proposed framework demonstrates that executable FB-based PLC logic can be generated from natural-language specifications without model fine-tuning. Future research will focus on automating the parsing of unstructured documents and integrating hybrid sequence logic to further improve the framework's scalability across maritime and industrial control systems.

Data Availability

The industrial control narratives, Function Block manuals, and field I/O datasets analyzed during the current study are subject to non-disclosure agreements with the equipment vendors and the shipyard. Therefore, the raw data cannot be made publicly available.

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